

Gender analysis

with

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At the University of Antwerp, we have some experience reflecting on new reproductive technologies and gender. Joke Struyf is writing a PhD on feminist approaches to motherhood. Kristien Hens has published on a wide range of topics within reproductive ethics (nuclear transfer for mitochondrial disease, preimplantation genetic testing, donor conception, termination of pregnancy, embryo editing...). In addition, she has conducted several qualitative studies with patients and fertility doctors. In the B2-Inf consortium, we enjoy working with people with similar and complementary expertise in European countries. We think this 'internationalization' of our experience is beneficial to all partners, not in the least to ourselves.

We cover many gender-related issues. However, there is always a temporal and contextual aspect to societal expectations. Even as we are analyzing the data, society changes, and our knowledge changes as we analyze data, qualitative research is, therefore, preferably an iterative process: it would be nice to be able to talk to the same people again and discuss recent societal trends, e.g. abortion issues or recent law changes regarding same-sex marriage and adoption (e.g. in Switzerland and Slovenia). Some gender aspects are difficult to compare because of the differences in participant samples. In some countries, like Italy and Spain, more than half of the participants identify as LGBTQ+. In other countries, all participants identify as heterosexual. Therefore, it is hard to compare results.

Moreover, some subjects are seldomly discussed, like multiple parenthood, in which case more than two partners are raising a child, for example, a lesbian couple and a gay couple, or a heterosexual couple with a known donor who likes to play an active role in the raising of the child, or several non-related people raising children together. The research provides us with a lot of data regarding gender roles and the expectations towards men and women. However, the focus of both interviewers and participants was predominantly on gender roles in cis/heterosexual, non-divorced relationships. Other relationships in which gender role traditions are less strict or not as relevant, for example, in LGBTQ+ parent families, multiple parent families or co-parenting ex-partners, were less represented in this research.

We have already identified some gaps in laws regarding infertility treatments. One is that LGBTQ+ people struggle with ART access just as much as with prejudices towards LGBTQ+ parenthood. Some of them might theoretically be able to become parents. Still, they fear the reactions of their neighbours and family or think that the unwelcome environment would lead to their children being bullied. The lack of information on surrogacy is another gap. We discovered that the invasiveness of procedures is sometimes represented differently, for example, when it entails an egg donation vis-à-vis a patient undergoing an IVF procedure. Women's bodies and body parts are described in great detail on clinics' websites. At the same time, the role of men, and especially the circumstances for obtaining a sperm sample, are often left unexplained. Another issue that came up is that fertility discourse is very binary. Non-binary, genderqueer and intersex people are absent from clinics' websites. Since fertility clinics deal with all kinds of fertility challenges, there is no reason why people identifying as different from the classic binary man or woman could not be welcomed there. B2-Inf's research offers an excellent starting point for changing the discourse to become more inclusive.

Of course. There is a discrepancy between what the young people think and what the 'traditional' society provides. Some of them will use fertility services in the future. We see that, especially in more conservative societies, they struggle with what is expected and what they would like to be the case. Our research points to a strong tension between the expectations that all women should become mothers and the idea that individuals can make their own choice. Most participants expect to become parents one day, an equal expectation for men and women, but they respect the will of people who do not like to become parents. Theoretically, many of them agree that becoming a parent should not be necessary to live a meaningful life. However, childless women, whether voluntary childless or not, are subject to many prejudices. They are seen as immature, not entirely a woman, or selfish. A woman's desire to become a mother is still seen as 'natural', so there must be something wrong with a woman who does not want children. Men, however, do not suffer from those prejudices. They can live a childless life that is regarded as meaningful. This tension is very gendered, and it seems to be impossible to overcome. While young women often strongly support the choice paradigm and reject societal expectations about motherhood, their own desire to become a mother is often equally strong and cannot easily be explained. Men's desire to have children is also strong, but they carry less responsibility and do not point towards tension.

Young people point to the fact that in heterosexual relationships, reproduction and raising children are much more of a woman's responsibility than a man's. Work/family tension is always perceived as a problem for mothers, not fathers. Most of the young people in our research think the responsibility should be shared between partners. Still, they are sceptical because they see traditional gender patterns reproduced in their social circle. For women, this is a serious concern.

In addition, in many societies, reproduction issues still are taboo, like other sexuality-related issues. People do not like to talk about it. Young people feel more open to discussing sexuality amongst their peers, indicating that older generations do not. However, infertility, and predominantly male infertility, is regarded as taboo, even in those younger generations. It is seen as a private matter and is kept between partners. There is a broader trend towards more patient-centred care in health care in general. In that respect, B2-Inf provides essential information for clinics and governments about the expectations of young people. It is evident that young people want detailed information on all ART options and want treatments to be accessible, regardless of income, sexuality, gender expression or marital status. To cater to this need, the project aims to provide essential data to work towards more inclusivity in assisted reproductive treatments.